

DEVELOPMENT OF SELECTION AND GROWING TECHNOLOGY OF NUT VARIETIES FOR SIRDARYA REGION

Qurbanov Ermamat Sayfiddinovich
Ungarov Azizbek Abdumo`min o`g`li
Zafarova Nozimakhon Khushyorjon qizi
Kholmatova Ozoda Zokir qizi

Gulistan State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8036083>

Annotation: Scientific research on the creation of promising varieties and forms of walnuts is widely developed in the countries of the world. This article provides information on the cultivation technology of Ideal and Tonskoskorlupii promising walnut varieties in the Syrdarya region.

Keywords: nut, variety, seed, root, seedling, tree, rootstock, fruit, peel, core, yield, productivity.

Introduction: Walnuts have been cultivated in Uzbekistan since ancient times. The tree is 25-30 meters tall, 1.5-2 meters in diameter, its branches are spherical or dome-shaped, rarely branches, the bark of old trees is cracked. The root system is strong, grows to a depth of 4 meters, spreads 10-15 meters around. At the base of the trunk and main branches, there are many dormant buds. Walnut trees begin to bear fruit in 8-10 years, grafted ones in 5-6 years. There are varieties that bear fruit in the 2nd year after transplanting. Nuts become fertile when they are 25-35 years old, and each bush yields 100-150 kg, and in some cases up to 300-500 kg. and one year there is a large harvest, and the second year there is a low harvest. The fruit ripens from the end of August to the beginning of October.

MAIN PART, RESULTS: Nuts are propagated from seeds and grafts. Nuts with thick skin and large seeds are selected. They do not lose their ability to germinate for up to a year. Sown in autumn, stratified. After about 20-25 days, the seed will turn blue at 18-20 degrees. The seeds with a very thin skin will germinate even if they are not stratified, but before sowing they are kept in running water for 3-4 days, and then planted in wet soil at a depth of 10 cm with a row spacing of 70 cm. The seeds are placed side by side with an interval of 10 cm. 900-1000 kg of walnuts are planted per hectare. A seedling grows slowly at first. It is watered at least 10 times during the growing season. They are grafted in the 2nd year. The first half of June-July is considered the most favorable time for welding, in which a special rectangular knife is used and a shield with buds 2.9x1.7 cm in size is cut, or a double knife with an interval of 2.9x3.0 cm is used. From the north side of the paywantg, a rectangular bark shield is cut from the bottom. It is the same from the graft, but the bark shield with buds is cut and placed on the cut of the graft. Then the graft is well wrapped with polyvinyl chloride film. Before and after planting, the seedlings are watered. After 2 weeks, the film is removed and the graft is cut 10-15 cm above the grafting site, then it grows. Seedlings and seedlings are grown on the basis of usual agricultural techniques. At the end of the second year, the seedlings reach 2 meters in height and are ready for planting in the garden. It is necessary to choose fertile lands with deep unsalted seepage waters for planting. The separated area should be well ventilated. Air must be well ventilated so that more harmful cold air mass does not accumulate. Walnuts can be

grown in mountainous regions with annual rainfall of 800 mm or more. The land for planting walnut seedlings is treated in the same way as for fruit crops.

№	Crop type	Planting scheme	Number of seedlings (meter)	range (meter)	Greens range (meter)	Definition
1	Walnut	10x8	125	10	8	When placing seedlings, it is recommended to plant depending on the caretakers
2	Walnut	8x8	156	8	8	

Walnut pulp is a very fatty and nutritious product, containing 60-70% oil, 11-20% protein, up to 20% carbohydrates and vitamins. Walnuts contain 3-5 times more vitamin C than walnuts. In terms of nutrition, walnuts are better than meat and close to butter. There are several varieties of walnuts. These are Vostandiksky, Ideal, Tonskoskorlupiy and Jubilee varieties. Currently, the Ideal and Tonskoskorlupi varieties of walnuts are planted in the Syrdarya region. The ideal variety was created at the Bostanliq mountain scientific-experimental station of the scientific-research institute of horticulture, viticulture and pomegranate growing named after Akademic M. Mirzayev.

After the seedling is planted, it begins to harvest very early, it begins to harvest in the first year. Since 1967, the Tonskoskorlupiy variety has been included in the State Register of Adijan, Jizzakh, Kashkadarya, Namangan, Samarkand, Surkhandarya, Syrdarya, Tashkent and Fergana regions. It begins to bear fruit in the sixth year after planting.

Walnut variety	Tree	Fruit	Taste assessment of the fruit	Productivity	
				In eight years	In ten years
Ideal variety	Tall, with broad ovate branches	Flat round	4.6 ball	3.3 kg	12-13kg
Tonskoskorlupiy variety	Tall, with wide branches, spherical	Wide ovoid, light green		3.3 kg	12-13 kg

Conclusion: As a result of studying early harvest and productivity of walnut varieties, Ideal and Tonskoskorlupiy varieties of walnut were studied. As a result of the research, the Ideal variety was selected for cultivation in the Syrdarya region due to its early harvest, average yield, and easy separation of the kernel from the shell of the nut compared to other nuts.

References:

- 1.The basics of fruit growing T.E Astanaqulov S.X Narziyeva Tashkent-2010-B.183-186
- 2.Population field networks and farms recommendation on important agrotechnical activities in gardens and vineyards A.Nishanov Namangan-2010-B.21
- 3.Catalog of recommended fruit and grape varieties for planting in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan Tashkent-2016-B. 71
- 4.Adhamov, Azizjon, Azizbek Ungarov, and Ibrohim Jo'lbekov. "PROSPECTS OF USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN AGRICULTURAL SECTOR DEVELOPMENT." Journal of Agriculture & Horticulture 3.4 (2023): 13-15.
- 5.Ungarov, Azizbek. "INNOVATIVE METHODS OF FRUIT AND VEGETABLE PROCESSING." International Conference On Higher Education Teaching. Vol. 1. No. 2. 2023.
- 6.Jo'lbekov, I., Ungarov, A., Umrzoqova, I., & Adhamov, A. (2023). UZUMNING SANOATBOP NAVLARINI YETISHRISH USULLARIGA DOIR MAVZULARNI INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANGAN HOLDA TASHKIL ETISH. Евразийский журнал технологий и инноваций, 1(6), 89-93.
- 7.Qurbanov, E., Ungarov, A., Zafarova, N., & Xolmatova, O. (2023). AGRAR SOHADA RESURSLARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH TEXNOLOGIYALARI TAHLILI. Евразийский журнал технологий и инноваций, 1(6), 143-146.
- 8.Рахматов О. и др. Разработка трёхвалкового аппарата для пластификации вяленой дыни //Наука, техника и образование. – 2019. – №. 9 (62). – С. 41-43.

9. Курбонов Э. ОБОСНОВАНИЕ ШИРИНЫ МЕЖДУСЛЕДИЯ ЗУБЬЕВ
РЫХЛИТЕЛЯ НА ВЕСНОГО БОРОНОВАЛЬНОГО АГРЕГАТА // Eurasian Journal of Academic
Research. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 997-1002.

10. Рахматуллаев Р. К., Жўлбеков И. С., Адхамов А. Р. МЕТОДИКА ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ
АЭРОДИНАМИЧЕСКОГО ПОЛЕТА СУШЕНОЙ ВИНОГРАДНОЙ ЯГОДЫ // Евразийский
журнал академических исследований. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 3 Part 2. – С. 147-151.

